

FLUIDITY AND TEMPERATURE. PART II. CASES OF MERCURY AND GALLIUM AND A GENERAL CRITIQUE

BY ASOKK KUMAR MUKHERJEE

The equation developed in Part I of this series connecting fluidity and temperature has been tested in the cases of mercury and gallium which are monatomic liquids with extensive range of stability, and the results interpreted.

In a critical review of the theoretical relations connecting temperature and viscosity of liquids, Srinivasan and Prasad (*Phil. Mag.*, 1942, 33, 258) tested the validity of different equations by examining the cases of liquid metals, specially gallium, which exists in the liquid state for the widest range of temperature under atmospheric pressure. In the light of the remarks made by the authors, the equation derived in Part I (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 519) and verified in Part III of this series of communications (to be published later) has been verified in the cases of mercury and gallium. The present communication embodies the results of this attempt and a critical review of the equations proposed and the results obtained as presented in three different parts of this series.

Cases of Mercury and Gallium

In Part I, the following equation connecting fluidity (ϕ) and free energy (G) of a liquid has been derived.

$$\log \phi + \frac{3}{2} \log T - \log \frac{NAh^3}{(2\pi mk)^{3/2}} - \log f_v - \log f'_v + \frac{\Delta E_o - G}{2.303RT} \dots \dots (1)$$

where T is the absolute temperature; N , the Avogadro's number; A , a constant for the liquid; h , the Plank's constant; m , the mass of a single molecule; k , the Boltzmann constant; f , the partition function for interatomic vibrations in a molecule; f'_v , the partition function for intermolecular vibrations amongst different molecules; ΔE_o , the internal latent heat of vaporisation and R , the gas constant.

In the case of normal liquids, where the vibrational partition functions are usually small and the changes in these quantities with temperature are also small, it has been possible to bring the above equation to the following form

$$\phi T^{\frac{3}{2}} = a_1 \exp (b_1/T) \dots \dots (2)$$

where a_1 and b_1 are two constants. In the case where temperature variations of these vibrational partition functions cannot be neglected, equation (1) yielded another relation

$$\phi T^{\frac{7}{2}} = a_2 \exp (b_2/T) \dots \dots (3)$$

where a_2 and b_2 are constants.

Equation (2) was tested in the cases of mercury and gallium by plotting $(\log \phi + \frac{1}{2} \log T)$ against $1/T$. In both cases (Figs. 1 and 2) the graphs appear

FIG 1

to be convex towards $1/T$ axis, and gallium shows this effect most prominently. This indicates that in these cases the observed effect is greater than that expected

FIG 2

from an application of equation (2). Equation (3) cannot be applied to these cases because being monatomic liquids, vibrational partition function would refer only to the energy of vibration between two atoms held together by Van der Waals' forces. The cause of anomaly, as referred to above, is therefore to be traced to certain other factors regarding which some tacit assumptions have been made in the derivation of equation (1).

On analysis it is evident that one such assumption is the linear variation of G with T , which can be justified only by way of approximation within a narrow temperature range. In cases like gallium and mercury, it appears that G should be expressed in a more general and explicit form wherein terms containing higher powers of T should be taken into account.

Expressing G as a function of T , let,

$$G = \lambda + \mu T + \xi T^2 + \dots$$

where λ, μ, ξ etc. are constants. Now that G is a finite quantity, the coefficients of the higher powers of T must vanish rapidly. Taking up to the second power* we get

$$G = \lambda + \mu T + \xi T^2$$

Using the value of G in equation (1), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \log \phi + \frac{1}{2} \log T &= \log \frac{NAh^3}{(2\pi mk)^{3/2} f_v f_v'} + \frac{\Delta E_0 - \lambda - \mu T - \xi T^2}{2.303 RT} \\ &= \alpha + \frac{\beta}{T} - \frac{\xi T}{2.303 R} \end{aligned}$$

where $\alpha = \log \frac{NAh^3}{(2\pi mk)^{3/2} f_v f_v'} - \frac{\mu}{2.303 R}$

and $\beta = \frac{\Delta E_0 - \lambda}{2.303 R}$

or $\log \phi + \frac{1}{2} \log T + \frac{\xi T}{2.303 R} = \alpha + \beta/T \dots \dots \dots (5)$

Again we know from thermodynamics that

$$(dG/dT)_p = -S$$

Hence from equation (4)

$$(dG/dT)_p = \mu + 2\xi T = -S$$

Hence the coefficient μ and ξ are negative. This conclusion is also arrived at from Nernst's heat theorem

$$\Delta G = H_0 - \beta T^2$$

whence the coefficient of T^2 is negative. Hence, it may be rightly concluded that ξ is a negative quantity and is equal to $-\xi'$ say.

Commonly the series up to the second power is enough as it is rapidly convergent and the coefficient of the third power is very small.

Hence the equation (5) becomes

$$\log \phi + \frac{3}{2} \log T - \frac{\xi' T}{2.303 R} = \alpha + \frac{\beta}{T} \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

Thus the plot of $(\frac{3}{2} \log T + \log \phi)$ against $1/T$ becomes convex as it always involves a certain quantity $-\xi' T/2.303 R$ which should be deducted in representing the actual behaviour of the metals, mercury and gallium. Equation (6) thus presents a plausible explanation of the behaviour of these metals. A closer examination of the equation has been possible in the case of mercury only, for which $\delta \left(-\frac{\xi' T}{2.303 R} \right)$ was calculated from the temperature variation of C_p . The value of δ is found to be 1.1×10^{-4} . In the case of gallium, however, the necessary data were not available.

Critique.—The relationship between fluidity and temperature has thus been investigated in Parts I to III of this series (*loc. cit.*) from a theoretical point of view by connecting this with free volume in a liquid in which the molecules of the liquid have been assumed to undergo translatory motion.

The free volume is again connected with the translatory partition function by Boltzmann statistics, and hence to the free energy of molecules. The relationship is thus not a simple one. Viscosity is ultimately connected with the probable energy states of the liquid molecule, and so the same equation is not likely to apply to all liquids nor to different ranges of temperature. In the present case one fundamental equation has been deduced which has been changed to different forms to suit different conditions. These equations again differ considerably from the classical equation of Andrade (*Phil. Mag.*, 1934, 17, 497, 696).

$$\phi = a \exp (\delta/T) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

where a and δ are constants. In the present case, the constant ' a ' has been shown to be a function of temperature. In cases of simple liquids T occurs in ' a ' with an index of $-3/2$, a conclusion also arrived at by Eyring (cf. Glasstone, Laidler and Eyring, "The Theory of Rate Processes", McGraw Hill Book Co., 1941, p. 486). In the case of associated liquids the same index has been shown to change to $-7/2$. Another interesting point in these equations is that, the constant ' δ ' has also been shown to be a function of temperature because it involves free energy G , and this has been helpful in understanding the behaviour in the cases of mercury and gallium. This point, that the constant ' δ ' probably involved T , was also suggested by different workers (Eyring *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, p 494; Eirich and Simha, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1939, 7, 116) from their experimental observations but none of them were quite definite on this point and no theoretical approach was presented to clarify this.

The different equations derived herein appear to be similar in many respects to some of those previously arrived at from different considerations. But in the method of derivation, as presented herein, no mechanism has

been assumed for the flow process; the equations follow purely from the unique assumption of translatory motion of liquid molecules in the free space available within. The fundamental equation arrived at in this manner has been flexible enough so that it has been possible to apply this to diverse cases of liquids at different temperature ranges. The same fundamental equation has been helpful in connecting viscosity with different other properties of the liquid state as will be evident in subsequent communications. The question of fluidity and external pressure has already been discussed in a previous communication (*Trans. Indian Inst. Chem. Eng.*, 1950, 2, 36).

Moreover, these equations, specially the equations (2) and (3), can be put in a general form:

$$\log \phi = A_1 + \frac{B_1}{T} + C_1 \log T$$

where A_1 , B_1 and C_1 are constants, which is of the identical form as the three-constant-equation derived empirically and referred to by Madge and others (*Physics*, 1934, 5, 39) and believed to be of greater accuracy by Friend ("Text Book of Physical Chemistry", Griffin, 1932, p. 247). In fact, in these communications the empirical three-constant-equation has been given a theoretical footing.

Author's thanks are due to Prof. S. N. Mukherjee, and to Prof. S. R. Palit for their valuable help and guidance and to the authorities of the institution for granting him the facility to use the library and the laboratory.

PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY,
JADAVPUR, CALCUTTA—32.

Received April 9, 1951.